

HyDelta 3

WP 3B – Ammonia Future proof commodity – Direct Utilization and Conversion to Hydrogen

D3.2 – Ammonia Utilization in the power sector

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Executive summary

By 2035, the Dutch 'Nationaal Plan Energiesysteem' envisions flexible electricity generation from hydrogen, when renewable electricity supply is low. The hydrogen would be combusted in retrofitted gas-fired powerplants, fuelled from the hydrogen backbone. It is likely that a substantial fraction of total European hydrogen consumption will rely on overseas import in the form of ammonia. The ammonia would be converted to hydrogen in 'cracker' plants at the port of entry and fed to the backbone. The availability of large quantities of ammonia raises the question of whether ammonia-fuelled powerplants could be a plausible alternative to hydrogen-fuelled plants. Overland transport of large quantities of ammonia is complicated because of its toxicity. However, close to the port of entry such plants might potentially be attractive.

One option is to closely integrate a hydrogen-fired gas turbine with an ammonia cracker, so that the high temperature heat from the turbine exhaust can be used to drive the cracking process. This increases the overall system efficiency compared to stand-alone cracker and hydrogen-fired turbine.

Another option is direct ammonia combustion. Although ammonia co-firing in coal powered plants is an active topic of research, we could find no reports on the development of 100% ammonia-fired boilers for use in powerplants. By contrast, several companies report working on 100% ammonia-fired turbines. The main technological challenge is the development of a combustor that prevents excessive NOx production. It seems unlikely that this technology reaches the required maturity by 2035.

Samenvatting

Tegen 2035 voorziet het Nederlandse 'Nationaal Plan Energiesysteem' dat flexibele elektriciteitsopwekking uit waterstof benodigd is wanneer de levering van hernieuwbare elektriciteit laag is. De waterstof zou verbrand kunnen worden in aangepaste gasgestookte elektriciteitscentrales, gevoed vanuit het waterstof netwerk. Het is waarschijnlijk dat een substantieel deel van het totale Europese waterstofverbruik zal afhangen van overzeese import in de vorm van ammoniak. De ammoniak zou in 'cracker'-installaties in de binnenkomende havens worden omgezet in waterstof en naar de waterstof backbone worden gevoerd. De beschikbaarheid van grote hoeveelheden ammoniak roept de vraag op of door ammoniak aangedreven elektriciteitscentrales een plausibel alternatief kunnen zijn voor door waterstof aangedreven centrales. Het over land transport van grote hoeveelheden ammoniak is ingewikkeld vanwege de toxiciteit. Echter, dicht bij de binnenkomende haven kunnen dergelijke installaties mogelijk aantrekkelijk zijn.

Een optie is om een door waterstof aangedreven gasturbine nauw te integreren met een ammoniakcracker, zodat de hoge temperatuurwarmte van de turbine-uitlaat kan worden gebruikt om het krakingsproces aan te drijven. Dit verhoogt de algehele systeemefficiëntie in vergelijking met een op zichzelf staande kraker en waterstofgestookte turbine.

Een andere optie is directe ammoniakverbranding. Hoewel ammoniak co-verbranding in kolengestookte centrales een actief onderzoeksgebied is, konden we geen rapporten vinden over de ontwikkeling van 100% ammoniakgestookte ketels voor gebruik in elektriciteitscentrales. Daarentegen melden verschillende bedrijven te werken aan 100% ammoniakgestookte turbines. De belangrijkste technologische uitdaging is de ontwikkeling van een verbrandingskamer die overmatige NO_x-productie voorkomt. Het lijkt onwaarschijnlijk dat deze technologie tegen 2035 voldoende ontwikkeld is voor inzet op grote schaal.

Table of contents

Document summary	2
Executive summary	3
Samenvatting.....	4
1. Introduction	6
2. Hydrogen Value Chain.....	6
3. Options for direct use of ammonia	8
3.1 Integrated Reformer.....	8
3.2 Direct Combustion of ammonia	8
4. Conclusion	10
References.....	12

1. Introduction

As outlined in the Dutch 'Nationaal Plan Energiesysteem' (NPE) [1], by 2035 hydrogen will play a vital role not only as an industrial feedstock but to provide dispatchable electricity during periods of low renewable electricity production as well. Hydrogen has the potential to decarbonize existing gas turbine facilities by retrofitting amongst others the combustion chamber and fuel supply system. The fast start-up and load-changing capabilities of gas turbines can supplement an electricity system based on intermittent renewable sources.

By utilizing hydrogen-fired dispatchable assets, the need for flexibility shifts from the electricity system to the hydrogen system. Therefore, flexibility is required in the hydrogen system either through storage or flexible supply.

The NPE outlines that the future installed capacity of wind and solar in the Netherlands is deemed insufficient to cover the expected hydrogen demand. Therefore, it is envisioned that hydrogen will be imported to supplement national production.

To transport hydrogen, it is likely to be converted to an energy carrier, liquefied or transported by pipeline (when transportation distance allows). One likely pathway to transport hydrogen as an energy carrier is through production and shipping of ammonia. At the port of entry, the ammonia has to be reconverted to hydrogen through reforming (often referred to as cracking). The hydrogen is subsequently transported and distributed through the hydrogen backbone to industry, powerplants and other off takers.

However, the import of large quantities of ammonia also raises the possibility of using ammonia directly for power generation thereby reducing the need for purification or reforming. This document outlines the main configurations for the direct use of ammonia in the power sector. It discusses the main advantages and disadvantages, the state of technology, in order to assess the relevance for the Dutch electricity sector.

2. Hydrogen Value Chain

The value chain of hydrogen-fired power plants based on imported ammonia is presented in Figure 1. Ammonia from the terminal at the point of entry is reconverted to hydrogen in the reformer. To meet the specification of the hydrogen backbone [2], the effluent of the reformer needs to be purified. The purified hydrogen is subsequently fed to the hydrogen backbone. From the backbone, hydrogen is extracted and fed to a powerplant, for example a retrofitted combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) [3]. Alternatively, hydrogen from the backbone could be converted to electricity in a co-generation unit (combined heat and power) or potentially fuel cells (although the latter have not been deployed at the powerplant-scale).

Hydrogen has a higher lower-heating value and a higher burning velocity than methane. This results in a higher flame temperature than natural gas. A higher flame temperature leads to increased NO_x formation and therefore the combustor of the gas turbine has to be designed specifically in order to meet NO_x emission requirements. Figure 2 presents an overview of the development schedule for hydrogen-fired gas turbines as reported by Mitsubishi Heavy Industries [4]. This figure shows the development hydrogen-firing capabilities of middle and large gas turbines. For mid gas turbines it is expected to have 100% H₂-firing in the upcoming years. For larger gas turbines it is expected to be able to operate 100% on hydrogen from 2030 onwards.

Hydrogen based value chain

Direct use of ammonia

Figure 1: Hydrogen Value Chain based on ammonia import and hydrogen backbone distribution

Figure 2: Development schedule for hydrogen - fired gas turbines according to Mitsubishi Heavy industries [4]

3. Options for direct use of ammonia

Ammonia can be used in the power sector mainly in two different configurations as outlined in Figure 3. In the first configuration of Figure 3, an ammonia reformer (or ‘cracker’) and a hydrogen-fired CCGT are integrated into a single plant. In the second configuration of Figure 3, ammonia is combusted directly. These two configurations are discussed in more detail in the following paragraphs.

Figure 3: Two combustion strategies for gas turbines outlined by Mitsubishi Heavy Industries [4]

3.1 Integrated Reformer

The integrated reformer configuration aims to integrate the reformer and the powerplant. By integrating the reformer with a CCGT, high temperature exhaust heat from the gas turbine can be used to drive the reforming process. This potentially improves the overall energy efficiency. In addition, by integrating the reformer with the CCGT, the hydrogen does not have to adhere to the backbone quality specification. Therefore, the hydrogen fed to the gas turbine can be of lower quality than that of the hydrogen backbone. Lower quality reduces the need for additional purification after the reforming process. Typically, such purification is done through pressure swing adsorption (PSA). The integration of the reformer and the powerplant does entail that the reformer will run in tandem with the powerplant. Since hydrogen-fired CCGTs are meant to supplement renewable electricity flexibly, the reformer will not run continuously and has to be designed with flexibility in mind.

3.2 Direct Combustion of ammonia

The direct combustion configuration aims to utilize ammonia directly without incurring the energetic cost of reforming. Ammonia can be converted to electricity through combustion in gas turbines, fired boilers, or electrochemically in fuel cells. Fuel cells capable of using ammonia directly are of a relatively low technology readiness level of 3 to 4 [5] and are therefore descope in this study.

Ammonia has a lower heating value and burning velocity than methane and hydrogen [6]. Overall, ammonia is more difficult to burn compared to hydrogen, methane and propane [6]. The main final combustion products of ammonia are water and nitrogen. However, burning ammonia using regular lean, pre-mixed combustion technologies leads to NO_x emissions which are 1-2 orders of magnitude higher than when natural gas is used [7]. Both gas turbines and fired boilers suffer this challenge of NO_x emissions, which stem from the fuel-bound nitrogen. Development of technology required to mitigate NO_x emissions is an ongoing effort.

NO_x production in ammonia flames sharply peaks at an ammonia/air equivalence ratio close to unity; for both fuel-rich and fuel-lean mixtures, NO_x production is very low [7]. This phenomenon is exploited in the staged combustion technology shown in Figure 5. For this technology, the primary chamber operates at fuel-rich conditions, resulting in unburned fuel in the form of hydrogen and nitrogen. This mixture is quenched with the remaining excess air to fuel lean condition. Hence, the secondary combustion stage operates at fuel-lean conditions which minimizes NO_x production. This staged combustion method is often referred to as rich-quench-lean combustion technology.

Figure 4: Staged combustion concept with a rich & lean zone [4]

For industrial furnaces or boiler type configurations, a similar concept to the rich-quench-lean method is used as exemplified by the Stoichiometric Controlled Oxidation technology from Duiker Combustion Engineers [8].

Mitsubishi is currently developing the combustor as shown in Figure 6 for ammonia, which targets small-to-middle class gas turbines. Initial tests are scheduled for 2024. After which the development will be continued with the view to enabling operation in actual unit and eventually to commercialisation from 2025 and onwards. Similarly, GE have announced the development of 100% ammonia fired gas turbines [9].

Burners are developed for the co-combustion for ammonia in coal powerplants. IHI and JERA have started a demonstration of co-firing 20% ammonia in a coal power plant [10]. Similar projects have been announced across Asia [11]. Specific research and development of 100%-fired boilers for power generation have not been conducted due to concerns about the generation of N₂O, which is a strong greenhouse gas [12].

Figure 5: Development schedule for direct ammonia combustion as outlined by MHI [4]

4. Conclusion

To meet the future hydrogen demand it is envisioned in the Dutch ‘Nationaal Plan Energiesysteem’ that imported hydrogen is required to supplement national production. Ammonia can be imported as a hydrogen carrier but requires reconversion at the port of entry and subsequent distribution through the hydrogen backbone. This hydrogen can be extracted from the backbone to provide electricity during periods of low renewable electricity supply. Alternatively, ammonia can be directly used in power plants in two main configurations: 1) integrated reformer and 2) direct ammonia combustion.

The integrated ammonia reformer combines the reformer (or cracker) and the gas turbine. The extraction of high temperature heat from the turbine increases the overall system efficiency. Since overland transport of ammonia is complicated because of its toxicity, integrated reformers are best suited near the port of entry of ammonia whilst inland powerplants can be fed from the backbone.

Direct ammonia combustion can either be in a gas-turbine or in boiler-type powerplants. However, fuel-bound nitrogen increases potential NO_x emissions and such turbines are still in active development: mitigation of these NO_x emissions is inherently more difficult than those of hydrogen-fired turbines. Therefore, it is expected that hydrogen-fired turbines reach maturity more rapidly than ammonia-fired turbines. Boiler-type configurations enabling the co-firing of ammonia in coal power plants are an active topic of research, but there are concerns with regard to N₂O production at 100% ammonia.

Table 1 summarises the advantages and disadvantages of the different configurations for the utilisation of ammonia in the power sector. To provide a more detailed analysis on the most cost-effective solution to provide flexibility to the electricity grid a techno-economic assessment is recommended.

Table 1 : Overview of advantages and disadvantages of different ammonia reformer configurations

Configuration	Advantages	Disadvantages
Backbone connected reformer (baseline)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexible utilisation of hydrogen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low load factor when operated in tandem with flexible assets - Hydrogen storage required when operated continuously
Standalone integrated reformer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduced purification requirement would eliminate need for PSA - Exhaust heat gas turbine utilised during reforming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lock-in to provide hydrogen for powerplant - Low load factor when powerplant is operated as dispatchable asset - Location near ammonia terminal limits potential deployment
Backbone connected integrated reformer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexible deployment of hydrogen - Bypass PSA when electricity is produced - Exhaust heat gas turbine utilised during reforming during powerplant mode 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PSA required to feed into the hydrogen backbone - Heat requirement during hydrogen deployment for backbone - Location near ammonia terminal limits potential deployment
Direct ammonia combustion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No reformer required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased NOx emissions require additional mitigation measures - Location near ammonia terminal limits potential deployment

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